

Circuit Quantum Electrodynamics and Quantum Gates *

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May 15, 2026

Abstract

Circuit quantum electrodynamics is the study of nonlinear superconducting circuits, meaning circuits that behave like artificial atoms, and quantized electromagnetic fields within the microwave frequency range. This discipline adapts the concepts of cavity QED, replacing natural atoms with electronic devices made of superconducting materials that allow the observation of quantum phenomena at a macroscopic scale. This document aims to expand the study of these systems from a more fundamental perspective, focusing on one of the most essential components of these circuits: the Josephson junction, which acts as a nonlinear inductor, allowing the generation of a non-equidistant energy spectrum necessary for artificial atom behavior. Among qubit designs, the transmon qubit stands out because of its insensitivity to external charge noise and its long coherence times. The fundamental interaction between light and matter in these systems is described by the Jaynes-Cummings model, which explains the energy exchange between the qubit and an electromagnetic field inside a cavity.

Keywords: Quantum electrodynamics, Circuits, Electromagnetic fields, Superconductors.

1 Introduction

Circuit quantum electrodynamics (cQED) emerges as an adaptation of atomic cavity QED, which investigates the coherent interaction between individual atoms and quantized radiation fields. In this new paradigm, atomic systems are replaced by superconducting circuits, electronic devices made of materials that, at low temperatures, conduct electricity without resistance and allow the observation of quantum phenomena at the macroscopic scale (Nielsen & Chuang, 2000).

The fundamental element of these circuits is the Josephson junction Josephson (1962). Unlike conventional linear inductors, this junction acts as a nonlinear inductor whose inductance depends on the magnetic flux passing through it. This nonlinearity is essential for generating a non-equidistant energy spectrum, allowing the circuit to behave as an artificial atom.

On the other hand, the qubit, the basic unit of quantum information, interacts with microwave photons confined in high-quality resonators. The transmon qubit Koch et al.

*This research was supported by the Departamento de Ciencias Básicas of the Unidades Tecnológicas de Santander

(2007) is the most common type of qubit. This type of qubit is an artificial atom designed to be insensitive to external charge noise, which makes it the most widely used due to its relevance in quantum information processing and its long coherence times.

In conclusion, the study of light-matter interaction in cQED focuses on the dynamics between these nonlinear superconducting circuits and quantized electromagnetic fields in the microwave domain. This interaction is based on the Jaynes–Cummings model, which describes the coherent exchange of energy between a two-level system (such as a superconducting qubit) and a single quantized mode of an electromagnetic field inside a cavity Blais, Grimsmo, Girvin, and Wallraff (2021).

2 LC Oscillator

LC oscillator is a circuit with discrete elements (individual components) characterized by an inductance (L) and a capacitance (C). It is described by two fundamental variables:

- Charge (Q): The charge stored in the capacitor.
- Flux (Φ): The magnetic flux passing through the inductor.

There is a direct relationship between the LC oscillator and the mechanical oscillator. In a conventional mechanical oscillator, there is a mass-spring system oscillating, meaning that its position varies over time. In the case of an LC oscillator, the position is associated with the flux (Φ), the conjugate momentum with the charge (Q), and the mass with the capacitance (C).

Based on the above, it is necessary to describe the potential. In this type of system, the inductive energy acts as the harmonic potential. Unlike nonlinear systems, such as the previously mentioned transmon, the potential of an LC oscillator is perfectly quadratic with respect to the flux. Therefore, it can be expressed as:

$$V(\Phi) = \frac{\Phi^2}{2L} \quad (1)$$

The previous equation indicates that the resulting energy levels are uniformly distributed as: $\hbar\omega_r$. On the other hand, the Hamiltonian that represents the total energy of the system is divided into two main parts, corresponding to the stored electric and magnetic energy, respectively, as shown below:

$$H_{LC} = \frac{Q^2}{2C} + \frac{\Phi^2}{2L} \quad (2)$$

Where $\frac{Q^2}{2C}$ is the kinetic energy, following the analogy with the mechanical system, and represents the energy stored in the electric field of the capacitor. Meanwhile, $\frac{\Phi^2}{2L}$ is the potential energy, which can also be written as: $\frac{1}{2}C\omega_r^2\Phi^2$, highlighting its nature as a harmonic oscillator.

To operate in the quantum regime, the charge and flux variables are promoted to non-commutative operators: (\hat{Q} and $\hat{\Phi}$), which satisfy the relation: $[\hat{\Phi}, \hat{Q}] = i\hbar$.

Thus, the Hamiltonian can finally be expressed in terms of the creation (\hat{a}^\dagger) and annihilation (\hat{a}) operators as:

$$\hat{H}_{LC} = \hbar\omega_r \left(\hat{a}^\dagger \hat{a} + 1/2 \right) \quad (3)$$

Where \hat{a}^\dagger creates a photon with frequency ω_r in the circuit, representing a quantized excitation of the electromagnetic fields.

Thus, the Hamiltonian that describes the energy of this transmon can finally be expressed as:

$$\hat{H}_T = 4E_C (\hat{n} - n_g)^2 - E_J \cos \hat{\phi} \quad (4)$$

Where $E_C(\hat{n})$ represents the charging energy required to add a Cooper pair to the system and is defined by the total capacitance of the circuit. $E_J \cos \hat{\phi}$ is the Josephson energy, which is proportional to the rate at which Cooper pairs tunnel through the junction. Finally, n_g is the offset charge, which represents charge fluctuations in the qubit's environment.

Additionally, one of the main characteristics of the transmon is that it operates in a regime where the Josephson energy is much greater than the charging energy: ($E_J/E_C \gg 1$). This means that the system becomes insensitive to external charge fluctuations and, at the same time, solves the critical problem of previous designs, where electrical noise continuously altered the qubit frequency.

In conclusion, the transmon is an anharmonic oscillator specifically designed to suppress environmental noise, allowing coherence times long enough to perform complex quantum computing operations.

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